

Ability and Learner Identity in Irish Primary Mathematics Classrooms

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Children are constructed as learners of mathematics by virtue of their participation within the classroom. Through its modes of measurement, discipline, sanctions and rewards, the discourse of mathematics classrooms make children visible as mathematically (dis)abled subjects. From this discourse “ability” emerges. Teachers transmit their own values and definitions of ability to their class. Children come to view themselves as learners of mathematics through the messages communicated by their teacher and through comparison with their peers. This study employs a mixed methods design approach (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009) across eight primary school classrooms at second and fifth class level in DEIS and non-DEIS schools. A total of twenty-four mathematics lessons were observed, while eighteen mathematics lessons were video recorded. Focus group interviews with children, child questionnaires and drawings were also employed in the data collection. Eight teachers and eight school principals were interviewed. This paper will examine the discourse around ability by drawing on the perspectives of teachers and children.

Ability and Learner Identity

According to social practice theory, students come to the classroom as part of many diverse communities in which they have formed their identities and they have to reshape their identities as they participate in the community of the classroom. It is in this reshaping of identity that learning resides (Lee, 2006). “Identities are constructed within a context of activity, pupils build an identity, that is a way that they explain themselves, within each community in which they participate” (Holland et al., 1998 p.270). Similarly, “Mathematics in practice becomes an issue of identity as well as cognitive process” (Barta & Bremner, 2009 p.91). Enabling students to build an identity as someone who is able to do mathematics is an important aim for a mathematics classroom. Teachers are the most important resource for developing student mathematical identities (Cobb & Hodge, 2002; Hayes, Mills et al., 2006). They influence the ways in which student’s think of themselves as learners (Walshaw, 2004). While learning mathematical skills and knowledge, students are also developing beliefs and attitudes about the subject, and themselves as mathematical learners and practitioners (Grootenboer, 2013). Teachers of mathematics are in a powerful position because they can significantly impact on the mathematical identity and the futures of learners through the nature of the relational pedagogy they practice in their classrooms. This is evident throughout the everyday, routine mathematics classes that teachers and students experience. Feedback is a crucial feature of the teaching-learning process. Bloom (1976) identifies feedback, correctives and reinforcements as important elements of the instructional process. Feedback is considered to be one of the structuring conditions for learning, and is included alongside such variables as task presentation, sequencing, level and pacing of content and teacher expectations (Gipps & Tunstall, 1998). A major determinant of self-esteem is feedback from others, therefore children’s self-evaluations are very often a reflection of significant others’

evaluations, such as parents, teachers and peers. As far as academic self-esteem is concerned, teachers' evaluations are the most important, particularly in the early years of schooling. Children develop their 'self-image' in school through observing and feeling not only how the teacher interacts with them, but also how the teacher interacts with the rest of the class (Crocker & Cheeseman, 1988). The development of a positive self-concept in children is dependent upon perceiving themselves as successful, this in turn may depend on the way the child interprets the teachers' reaction to his/her performances. Often teachers, students and parents speak about success in mathematics education with reference to the concept of talent and of an inborn capability of mathematical thinking (Gellert et al., 2001). According to Boaler (2013), mathematics is a subject area that communicates the strongest fixed ability messages and thinking. Repeated teacher references to the "difficulty" of a particular mathematics text can serve as regulative discursive moves that position students and teachers in relation to cultural norms regarding ability and achievement (De Freitas, 2010). Through classroom practices messages are constantly communicated to children by teachers and schools regarding their ability and learner identity and this is succinctly summarised by Meighan and Siraj-Blatchford (1998) who argue that:

...pupils tend to perform as well, or as badly, as their teachers expect. The teacher's prediction of a pupil's or group of pupils' behaviour is held to be communicated to them, frequently in unintended ways; thus influencing the actual behaviour that follows. (p. 309).

This is particularly demonstrated in the grouping of students for mathematical learning where students of similar 'ability' are placed in different ability groups and whose later differing achievement has been attributed to the grouping effect. A Foucaultian reading of this situation sees students as subjects taking up top-middle-bottom positions that the discourses of classroom, school and home create and maintain in practice, normalising the structure that establishes and then perpetuates the inequality. Schooling more openly acts as a discursive domain productive of the mathematically able being such as the 'numerate child', created and maintained through a framework of practices of assessment (standardised testing and teacher designed tests). Dowling (1998) challenged the notion of "ability" as fixed and viewed schools as endeavouring to categorise and separate students, especially through the teaching of mathematics. According to Walls (2009) the right/wrong nature of mathematics as presented by teachers, textbooks, families and peers through social interactions, significantly contribute to students' mathematical identities and construct themselves as a learner of mathematics. Rowland (1995a) argues that a child's level of mathematical competence cannot and should not be judged by the child's offering of a "correct answer". Rowland (1995a) suggests that when a child volunteers an answer that is not the "expected" teacher answer, it is important to investigate and explicate the child's thinking and reasoning behind it. With reference to the linguist Lakoff, Rowland (1995b) demonstrates how in oral explanations, students use "hedgies" as "a shield against being wrong" (p. 350). The rewards and privileges that come with being correct are great. Rowland (1995b) observes that there is a regrettable absence of regard for the role 'uncertainty' plays in the mathematics classroom. Teachers and in turn students fail to recognise that being in a state of "uncertainty" is a necessary

precondition to learning and that in “the making and learning of mathematics, uncertainty is to be expected, acknowledged and explicit” (Rowland, 1995b, p. 328). Recent research carried out by Boaler (2013) into ability and mindset in the mathematics classroom reveals that the types of tasks chosen by teachers communicate powerful messages regarding what mathematics and knowledge is important. Tasks convey what doing mathematics is all about. By engaging in tasks, students develop ideas about the nature of mathematics and mathematics learning (Anthony & Walshaw, 2009; Hodge et al., 2007). If children are assigned short, closed mathematics questions that have right or wrong answers and children are regularly getting them incorrect, it is very difficult to sustain the opinion that high achievement is possible with effort. In contrast, when tasks are open, with opportunities for learning, children can see the possibility of greater achievement and respond to these opportunities to improve (Boaler, 2013).

Methodology

In Irish primary schools, children are seldom consulted or given the opportunity to formally express or document their experience of learning in school. The pervasive social lens through which children’s learning is examined is an adult one. This study employs a mixed methods design approach (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009) across eight primary school classrooms at second (7- and 8-year olds) and fifth class level (10- and 11- year olds). To allow for comparative analysis of social contexts, it was necessary to enlist two DEIS schools and two non DEIS schools at both second and fifth class level. All eight research schools were co-educational. Pseudonyms were used for the research schools and participants.

Table 1

Overview of Research Schedule and Research Methodology

September	Piloting of Children Questionnaire & Visiting the research schools			
October	Schools	Visit One	Visit Two	Visit Three
	Roadstown Quarryfield Bridge St Brookwood Abbeyside Knockbrack Summerville Mount Eagle	Observation of Mathematics Lessons Children’s Drawings Focus Group Interviews	Observation of Mathematics Lessons Children’s Questionnaire Focus Group Interviews	Observation of Mathematics Lessons Focus Group Interviews
November	Teacher Interviews (6 female, 2 male)			
February	School Leader Interviews (4 male, 4 female)			
Quantitative Instrument Design	<i>Child Questionnaire n =164</i>		Quantitative Analysis SPSS	
Qualitative Instrument Design	<i>Classroom observations n =24 Child Drawings n = 144 Interviews with Children n = 40 Interviews with Teachers n = 8 Interviews with School Leaders n = 8</i>		Thematic Analysis -Nvivo Thematic Analysis - Nvivo Thematic Analysis - Nvivo Thematic Analysis - Nvivo Thematic Analysis - Nvivo	

Mathematical Ability: The Perspective of Teachers

Maths is a switch off thing...it develops as children go through school, being shown these mathematical things, seem complicated to them, try them and they get them wrong and feel like they have failed. So the next time they don't listen for as long...they say 'I'm not going to get this', or 'someone else is better at this than me', 'maths isn't my thing'...so they are being set up for failure (Tom, Principal, Roadstown, DEIS).

Teaching mathematics has "always been hard but in recent years with the addition of children with special needs in the class that's just making it certainly difficult" (Ms Rice, Brookwood, 2nd Class, non-DEIS). Schools in designated disadvantaged contexts embraced new initiatives and acknowledged that children "have the best of resources and excellent teachers" (David, Principal, Abbeyside, DEIS). However, in spite of this "it has all been a conundrum as to why our numeracy scores were so below the average" and "if they don't improve after all this [initiatives] there is no hope" (David, Principal, Abbeyside, DEIS). The dialogue in these schools revolve around performativity where educational success is that which can be measured and quantified. School leaders and teachers share clear views on mathematics which are both overtly and covertly transmitted daily across classrooms "it's hard enough to make maths interesting at the best of times. You either find it easy or you can find it very difficult" (Denis, Principal, Knockbrack, DEIS). Schools perpetuate the notion that people are "good" or "bad" at mathematics. The demarcation of people into "can" and "cannot" do mathematics suggests that very little can be achieved with children who are not innately adept at mathematics. Teachers shared a common discourse around ability. Ability was defined both positively and negatively. Positive attributes included being "high flyers", "very very good", "bright" and "stronger". The negative form of ability encompassed the innate "their own overall weakness", "low intelligence", being "less able", "weaker", "struggling with the curriculum" "lower achieving" and "not grasping the topics". Ability was also something that was measured in standardised tests "like you get from maybe the 7 or 8 Sten right down to not even registering on the scale you know" (Ms Cooper, Abbeyside, 5th Class, DEIS). For many teachers speed was synonymous with high ability "very quick you know they would be very quick working out answers" (Ms Keane, Knockbrack, 5th Class, DEIS). Teacher descriptions of children's progress in mathematics revealed much about how they viewed children's mathematical ability, the criteria for success or failure in mathematics and the labels and names used to classify children of differing ability. For some teachers, knowledge and competence revealed itself through the visible form of "hands up" and giving the "right answer". Firmly established across classrooms was the belief that in mathematics something was either right or wrong "Someone like Cody would be forever with his hand up to give you the answer and he'll always have the right answer" (Ms Bosworth, Bridge St, 2nd Class, non-DEIS). It was not uncommon for second-class children to have experienced anxiety when it came to mathematics. This was evident through classroom observations, children interviews and their drawings. The teacher recognised that anxiety and fear was something experienced by some children but in her accounts did not consider a possible connection between mathematics anxiety and teacher expectations:

Julie is the little girl I had in at the door today crying that she didn't do well but she'll sit back because she knows this is very hard. She won't want to come up and try the whiteboard, she would be the type of child who doesn't want to get things wrong... she is a perfectionist and so she doesn't want to be seen to get anything wrong. (Ms Rice, Brookwood, 2nd Class, non-DEIS).

In the senior classes teachers attributed ability and "being good" at mathematics to be the by-product of attentive listening and children's adherence to the classroom norms and rules:

Sarah...you wouldn't think that she was looking or listening. (Mr Keating, Summerville, 5th Class, non-DEIS).

Tom and Patrick I say the fact that they are able to listen very carefully and watch and maybe being able to translate that into their work that they can follow the method and then apply it themselves on their own individually. (Mr Keating, Summerville, 5th Class, non-DEIS).

For some fifth class teachers, a child's attitude towards mathematics was a significant factor in determining performance in the subject "Stephen would be quite weak... he would be quite negative towards maths...he would give up quite easily and he needs a lot of support just to keep him interested in it" (Ms Keane, Knockbrack, 5th Class, DEIS).

Throughout teachers' accounts was the implication that a lack of mathematical ability was solely the fault of the child and success in mathematics was the reward that came with "listening" and "paying attention". The association between teachers' own pedagogical practices and how it impacts upon children's learning was ostensibly absent from their accounts.

Children's Perspectives on Ability

You can pay attention and just not 'get' what is going on (Diana, 5th Class, Mount Eagle, Middle Class).

According to one child being good at mathematics was attributed to the innate ability of having "a good brain" (Tony, Roadstown, 2nd Class, DEIS). For many children at second and fifth class level their identity as learners of mathematics is determined by speed activities, "being right" and "never getting maths wrong". This is reflected in child accounts and drawings "I don't normally get things wrong" (Aidan, Brookwood, 2nd Class, non-DEIS) and "I don't think I am very good at maths because I don't think I'm very good at understanding it" (Julie, Summerville, 5th class, non-DEIS).

Figure 1*Getting Maths Right (Summerville, 5th Class, non-DEIS)*

Comparisons with peers emerge as children rank themselves often unfavourably against their peers. As early as second class, children reveal a fixed mind-set regarding their ability where people are categorised into those who “can” and “cannot” do mathematics. The day-to-day experiences of the mathematics classroom affirms children in their personal held views of their ability:

Researcher: Would you say you are good at maths Keith?

Keith: I’d say alright, wouldn’t be the best.

Cora: Well we have this real smart boy...Billy McCann and if you say real fast “what’s 12 multiplied by 2?”, he’d say the answer straight away.

Keith: Yeah he is smart. (Knockbrack, 5th Class, DEIS).

and

Researcher: How can you tell if somebody is very good at maths?

Amelia: The first person ready. The last person ready, they need help with maths most.

Jacob: With the two lads...it’s basically because they don’t listen.

Researcher: Okay, so listening is important.

Zain: I am finished like fifth.

Jacob: I am finished like sixth. (Abbeyside, 5th Class, DEIS).

Children could identify peers for whom mathematics was a challenge “Sometimes they find it very hard to do maths. It was never their favourite subject and they’re not good at it” (Zain, Abbeyside, 5th Class, DEIS). At the end of the third visit a girl spoke about a boy named Jeffrey and other children who sat at the same table whom she identified as “not good at maths” and explained that Eoin who is a good student “[Eoin] sits at their table to make them look smarter” (Abbeyside, 5th Class, DEIS).

Conclusion

Children in this study constructed an image of themselves as learners of mathematics through the messages communicated by their teachers and through comparison with their peers. As early as second class children in this study displayed fixed mindsets regarding their ability in mathematics and the day to day experiences in the classroom affirmed them in their personal held views of their ability. The challenge for schools is to examine the fixed mindset culture that exists and to move beyond practices that label or define some learners as deficit and encourage teaching practices that value thinking, struggles and varied learning pathways of all children.

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